

Maker or Breaker of Democracy: A Comparative Analysis of Modern Media in Autocracies and Democracies

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I dedicate this project to my parents who have spent their whole lives protecting democracy.

“I declare that this thesis has been composed solely by myself and that it has not been submitted, in whole or in part, in any previous application for a degree. Except where states otherwise by reference or acknowledgment, the work presented is entirely my own.”

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Abstract

This project compares usage of propaganda between autocracies and liberal democracies, a characteristic of media that has historically been ascribed to authoritarian practices. For the analysis I will be comparing the propaganda usage in news outlets of two liberal democracies and two authoritarian countries. I have used Siebert, Peterson, and Schramm's *Four Theories of the Press* in order to give insight into the media's role in each of the countries, as well as the ideal of journalism in mass media. I will expand on the theories and analyse how they fit into the discourse of the countries.

The research has identified that, in many ways, the press of liberal democracies and authoritarian countries end up resembling each other with their usage of propaganda. By venturing analysis, I give insight into the peculiarities of the propaganda usage of each different country and all of the ways in which propaganda is utilised. I give an overview of the dangers of liberal press that have been found in this research, basing my analysis off the theories of the press, as stated above.

Key words: liberal democracies, autocracies, propaganda, information dissemination, democratic threat, journalistic responsibility, watchdog role, agenda setting

Introduction

How do authoritarian and liberally democratic countries resemble each other? This is the bigger philosophical question that I base my research on since the two regimes differ from each other by default. The question remains, where is it they meet? This has already been answered by Laskin (2019) in his psychoanalytic approach to propaganda, and that is, that they meet in the very human notions of propaganda that become apparent in everything that human beings do.

Following this statement, I want to present the example of the coverage of Donald Trump, which the world has experienced since 2015. By now the world has experienced the constant news stream of Donald Trump for nine years. Being an anomaly in the United States' elections, with all his scandals and his newsworthiness; Donald Trump has secured his place in the world as the star of the media, whether it be negative on liberal sites or positive on American conservative, as goes the saying: "No press is bad press." (Scacco and Coe 2021; Patterson 2016; Reuning and Dietrich 2018) These are just a few of the many research papers written on Trump's appearance in the news, however, media has not seen much change since then. In accordance with the Libertarian Theory of the press (Siebert et al. 1963), news outlets are, as well as disseminating information, trying to entertain and gain sales, however, when does appealing to the reader get in the way of trustworthy news?

Carter and Carter (2018) have found that Fox News is roughly as pro-party as Russian news outlets are pro regime. This proves that propaganda levels are moderate in the U.S.. It has been found that visibility is a big reason why Trump has such a platform (Reuning and Dietrich 2018), visibility has been found to be a vital aspect of the communication process (Mateus 2017). Since American news outlets are able to draw as much attention to a populist leader like Trump, it should be highlighted how democracies without a public broadcasting service appeal to their market and whether it is potentially harmful to citizens and democracy. I will be assessing this by comparing press of autocracies to democracies.

In this research paper I will be analysing the representation of presidential electorates, government and political parties in news outlets; I will investigate how press in liberal democracies resemble authoritarian countries by analysing their texts for notions of propaganda, using content analysis. I will be using characteristics of propaganda from different works, which have assessed, both, liberal democracies as well as authoritarian countries. I will be retrieving results from the time span of two weeks before the election of a new president of each country in the years 2016-2018.

The countries I have used for this research are France, the United States, Russia and China, in order to have balanced results; each of the countries differ from each other in the model of the regime they belong in. I will be assessing this factor further in my findings and analysis section.

My literature review covers three points. The first is an introduction to three of the four theories of press of Siebert, Peterson and Schramm (1963), being the Authoritarian, Libertarian and

Social Responsibility Theory of the press. These are the theories that define the modern liberal democratic press. Secondly, I will briefly introduce propaganda in liberal democracies. Finally, I will introduce the characteristics of propaganda that I have used for this research and the works where they're derived from. For the characteristics used to conduct my research I read works that assessed authoritarian countries, as well as liberal democracies. I will be assessing the theories' role in journalism today, as well as discussing the characteristics by comparing the democracies and autocracies.

In my findings and analysis section I will be discussing five of the nine propaganda characteristics used in my research. The points being attributional framing and signalling derived from Boussalis', Dukalskis' and Gerschewski's (2023) paper on how the press assessed the power exchange in North Korea when Kim Jong Un succeeded his father; these entail signalling the government or political party's executive power and framing opposition. Media visibility, a concept derived from works of Patterson (2016) and Mateus (2017). Executive tone used, a characteristic derived from the content analysis method of Carter and Carter (2018), which assessed whether there was a difference of tone in different countries' news outlets when presenting the government. Finally I assessed the notion of supporting propaganda, as stated by Stanley (2005) in his book *How Propaganda Works*, entailing over emotionality in order to advance a cause.

Literature Review

Three points are disclosed in this section: i) Authoritarian, Libertarian and Social Responsibility Theories of Journalism ii) Propaganda in Liberal Democracies and iii) Characteristics of Propaganda.

The first section introduces the Authoritarian, Libertarian and Social Responsibility Theory of Siebert, Peterson and Schramm, derived from their book *Four Theories of the Press* (1963). This section entails the practise of these theories, as well as being a brief outline of the ideologies that each of the countries analysed in this research adhere to. The second section will inquire into propaganda in liberal democracies and the final section introduces the characteristics of propaganda that I have used for this research.

AUTHORITARIAN, LIBERTARIAN AND SOCIAL RESPONSIBILITY THEORY OF JOURNALISM

The Authoritarian Theory of Journalism, originally tailored for media within authoritarian regimes, has exerted a profound influence on press systems, extending its reach even into liberal democracies. Introduced by Siebert et al. in 1963, this theory posits that media outlets serve as conduits for advancing state doctrines and objectives. It underscores the alignment of communication units with governmental policies, emphasising their role in supporting state agendas. Initially, mass media cautiously adhered to national objectives, gradually evolving to become indispensable tools in state communication strategies.

In many liberal democracies, it has now become the basis of press systems and has continued to influence “the practices of a number of governments which theoretically adhere to libertarian principles.” (Siebert et al. 1963: 11)

In the early stages of mass media this purpose was carried out in a way that attempted to avoid any interference with the attainment of national ends and only in the later stages started to participate in the state’s communication process and utilise mass media.

The Authoritarian Theory states that: “The units of communication support and advance the policies of the government in power so that this government can achieve its objectives.” (1963: 18)

Authoritarian regimes employ diverse methods to control media, ranging from direct state ownership to semi-autonomous entities subjected to government surveillance. This control paradigm contrasts sharply with the Social Responsibility Theory, which shares concerns about preserving societal values but diverges in assigning responsibility for determining and achieving societal goals. While the Authoritarian Theory delegates these tasks to central authorities, the Social Responsibility Theory ascribes a more proactive role to the press in informing and engaging citizens. “Both agree that the press should not be permitted to degrade the culture of a nation, and both postulate that when definite goals for society are determined (by different methods, however) the mass media should not be permitted to interfere irresponsibly with the

accomplishment of these objectives.” (1963: 25) Social responsibility advocates ultimately do assume the democratic position that it is up to the citizen to form their decisions, and they charge the press with the duty of informing citizens.

Journalism played a key role in democratic revolutions and since then has been described as the defining characteristic of democratic political and media cultures within a functioning public sphere. (McNair 2009) The emergence of the Libertarian Theory coincided with the advent of functional democracies. A defining characteristic that sets the Libertarian Theory apart from the Authoritarian Theory is that it functions as an extra-legal check on the government. The pivotal role of journalism in democratic movements underscores its significance in nurturing democratic cultures and fostering public discourse. The press was to keep officials from abusing their power, and was set to be the watchdog over the workings of democracy. In the beginning of liberal societies, the success of democracy rested on informed citizens relying on the media to provide the public with educational materials.

At its core, the Libertarian Theory advocates for media freedom, emphasising its role in discovering truth, facilitating informed decision-making, and providing diverse perspectives. This approach prioritises freedom from governmental interference and opposes government monopolisation of communication channels. This type of journalism provides for a more informal type of control through the self-righting process and through the free competition in the marketplace of information, opinions and entertainment. All Libertarian Theorists agree that freedom of speech is not absolute but limited and determining the limitations on libertarian principles is the problem democratic societies face. This has led the countries to create laws like the defamation law that prohibits the press from attacking individuals of a society.

Under the libertarian concept the functions of the mass media of communication are to inform and to entertain. The third function is to provide an outlet for sales and advertising thus ensuring financial independence, meaning a defining aspect of libertarianism is opposing government monopolies of the avenues of communication.

In contrast, proponents of the Social Responsibility Theory acknowledge the need for some form of media regulation, advocating for self-regulation with limited governmental intervention.

The libertarian asserts that the less political authority has to do with the communication process, the better, while advocates of the Theory of Social Responsibility content that, “although libertarian principles may be basically sound, their operation in the complex of contemporary society demands some form of control, preferably by the media themselves with a benevolent government in the background unobtrusively checking the ground rules.” (1963: 26)

The Social Responsibility Theory was derived when news outlets became monopolistic, and the concept of mass media was established.

The Commission of the Freedom of Speech, a unit created for the control of mass media, has stated their five requirements from the press being: truthful and comprehensive accounts, that separate fact from opinion; be a forum of exchange and criticism without the advocacy of their own opinions, representing all opinions; project a ‘representative picture of the constituents of the society’; responsibility of clarifying the goals and values of the society; provide full access to information, being a wide distributor of news. (Siebert et al. 1963)

Hallin and Mancini (2004) have created the three archetypes of adhering to different standards of journalism that they have applied to different democratic countries. They are the Polarised Pluralist, Democratic Corporatist and Liberal.

The Polarised Pluralist and Democratic Corporatist follow the notion of the Social Responsibility Theory, meaning that they experience state intervention, while the Liberal does not.

PROPAGANDA IN LIBERAL DEMOCRACIES

Laskin’s (2019) paper Defining Propaganda: A Psychoanalytic Perspective has concluded that people are most of the time willing to believe propaganda due to the human need to belong somewhere. This goes directly against the ideals of libertarianism that have created the Libertarian Theory of the press, being that the reader can be subject to all viewpoints and aspects of information, and will ultimately make the right decision for the society they are living in basing it on their own conscience. (Siebert et al. 1963)

The hypodermic needle theory states that mass media has a direct impact on the reader, coinciding with Laskin's (2019) statement as well as being the basis of the Social Responsibility Theory, stating that the consumer is passive.

Stanley (2005) states that part of the danger of propaganda in liberally democratic societies is that propaganda is not recognised because it is not allowed. There has been debate over what to call propaganda in liberally democratic societies, as it is deemed a norm in authoritarian regimes in order to realise the goals of the state. "Many existing definitions fail to distinguish between propaganda and public relations as well as advertising, persuasion, political campaigning, or even psychological warfare." (Laskin 2019:1)

The idea of forwarding ideals of the state without interruption falls namely under the Authoritarian Theory and Social Responsibility Theory, the latter emphasising this only in times of need. The lines of the state blur in modern democracies' media as most experience intervention from the political elite. (Herman and Chomsky 1988; Akhvan-Majid 1991; Hallin and Mancini 2004)

Herman and Chomsky's (1988) five aspects of propaganda, in adherence to the economic, social and political agenda of the elites of a state, are: "news values set by a concentration of ownership; influence of advertising; reliance on only the powerful for information; flak against transgressors and an ethos to the country's values (in their work that analyses press in the United States it as an ethos against communism)."

CHARACTERISATIONS OF PROPAGANDA USED IN RESEARCH

From Stanley's book *How Propaganda Works* (2005) I have derived the characteristic of Supporting Propaganda. In his book he has described it the following way: "A contribution to public discourse that is presented as an embodiment of certain ideals, yet is of a kind that tends to increase the realization of those very ideals by either emotional or other nonrational means." (2005: 53) In his book he assesses propaganda in liberal democracies.

Carter and Carter's (2018) empirical research paper called "Propaganda and Electoral Constraints in Autocracies", outlines the following two criteria, which they used in their

methodology: article valency and executive tone used. In their paper they assessed the ways that different countries, authoritarian and democratic, presented their governments in the press.

The following five criteria were derived from Boussalis', Dukalskis' and Gerschewski's (2023) paper, "Why It Matters What Autocrats Say: Assessing Competing Theories of Propaganda". In this paper they analysed North Korea's press when the country was experiencing Kim Jong Un, the current leader, succeeding his father. This research aimed to understand the media's role in a totalitarian country when its central power is at its most fragile.

- i) Propaganda as signalling: in their research, a mode of asserting authoritarian government's absolute power on people.
- ii) Legitimation approach: a regime or the newspaper, in a liberally democratic society, needing to justify their rule or standing somehow.
- iii) Frame resonance to attract: attracting attention to the political party or regime and cause.
- iv) Frame resonance to distract: distract the attention of readers away from the power supported in the cause of any problems by connecting, aligning and explaining events and experiences, thus framing news.
- v) Attributional framing: creating a sense of us v them. In authoritarian regimes this is directed at enemies of the state; in the democratic liberal, to the opposite party.

The final characteristic of propaganda I will be analysing the articles for is 'visibility'. The concept of the importance of this criteria, has been derived from Mateus' paper "Visibility as a Key Concept in Communication and Media Studies" (2017). He has described it as a "possibility to envisage a collective synchrony of attention in relation to publicness."

Patterson (2016) has used this criteria in his research about the 2016 elections in the United States. From his work it can be concluded that this notion of propaganda is directly linked to agenda setting, due to the passive consumer whose news values are set by the attention that the media draws to a subject.

Methodology

The aim of this research was to compare the press of liberal democracies to those of authoritarian regimes, through an analysis and comparison of articles for propaganda about the government. For authoritarian regimes I analysed articles for the propaganda of the government as well as the electorates and for liberal democracies the political party that the news source supports and electorates. I used content analysis to conduct my research.

Choosing four different countries - two authoritarian countries and two liberal democracies, those being: China, Russia, America and France, I used the websites of the news outlets to conduct my research, with the only exception being France's *Le Monde*, which does not publish all of their articles online. I was able to access the newspapers of *Le Monde* using the Proquest library archive.

For Russia, I analysed the news outlets *RBK Daily* (right wing populism; economic liberalism) and *Rossiyskaya Gazeta* (big tent; Pro-Putin); for China, *People's Daily* (official daily of the CCP Central committee) and *China Daily* (English language national daily); for America, the two most widely circulated newspapers, *The Wall Street Journal* (right-leaning) and *The New York Times* (left-leaning); for France, again, the most widely circulated, *Le Figaro* (right-leaning) and *Le Monde* (left-leaning).

I stayed on the original website of all of the news outlets in foreign languages, using Google Translate to conduct my research. The only exception was China's *People's Daily* because I was not able to gain access to the archives on the Chinese website. Due to the amount of articles found on *People's Daily*, I ended up analysing 18 articles from each news outlet.

I analysed articles in the span of two weeks before the election of the president of each country in the years 2016 - 2018. Since all news outlets differ in their publication methods, the timeframe from which the results were retrieved differed.

The newspapers were analysed by using a random number generator to pick a number from 1-14 and subtracted that number from the election day. I did not conduct a selectivity of the articles that I ended up reading. I analysed all of the articles I came across that had mentioned the

government, political party or electorates, and included the ones in my research that had notions of propaganda.

On China's People's Daily, I could not retrieve results from one or two days, thus I ended up analysing data from the whole span of two weeks and for *China Daily*, results from one day. Since this research project does not entail how much data is received from one or two days, I tried to give a fair point system to the authoritarian as well as the democratic countries, balancing China's results with the Russian results, and retrieving results for both of the Russian news outlets from the span of the two weeks.

Russian elections were held on the 18th of March 2018. I analysed articles from the span of the two weeks for both of the news outlets.

Chinese election sessions were held from the 5th of March to the 20th 2018. For *People's Daily*, I ended up analysing articles from the whole span of the two weeks; for *China Daily* I was able to retrieve all of the articles from the 24th of February.

France's first round of elections was held on the 23rd of April 2017. For both *Le Monde* and *Le Figaro* the analysis was conducted on articles published on the 12th of April.

For the American elections, held on the 8th of November 2016, I analysed articles published from the 27th to the 29th of October in both *The New York Times (NYT)* and *The Wall Street Journal (WSJ)*.

While an article could be characterised by multiple criteria of propaganda, it could not be done so twice with the same characterisation for one article. For example, there may have been multiple cases of supporting propaganda in one article but that article would still amount to one case. However, the same article can, in addition to supporting propaganda, be using propaganda as signalling.

I decided to follow this outline in order to draw clear results from the 18 articles analysed. It is important to note, that these characteristics did tend to overlap, I tried my best to give a fair point scheme to each one.

Findings and analysis

The liberal democracies' newspapers differed in content and style but had more or less the same results. According to Hallin's and Mancini's model (2004) France's media belongs to the Pluralised Polarist archetype and the United States' to the Liberal.

In their model they have described the Polarised Pluralist as experiencing high political parallelism as well as a weaker sense of professionalism (the degree of autonomy in journalism, as well as public service-oriented journalists and ethical practices) and being subject to strong state intervention at times. The Liberal is described as not experiencing any political parallelism, having a strong sense of professionalism and not being subject to state intervention.

While the Polarised Pluralist abides by the Social Responsibility Theory due to the fact that they experience state intervention at times of need, considering all of the other aspects they're ascribed to, they abide by the theory to a lesser degree than the Liberal who does not experience political parallelism and has a strong showing of professionalism.

The two authoritarian countries differ in their media models as well. While Russia is a competitive democracy, and the government does not directly control all of the media, then China does. While not directly owning the media, Russia's communication channels are all owned by allies of the government. Both of the countries adhere to the Authoritarian Theory.

Russia's *RBK* used to be known for its investigative journalism, for which the last editor-in-chief was let go, after publishing an article that was invasive to the president. These are the types of tactics used in competitive democracies for media control (Akhrarkhodjaeva 2017). *RG* is government owned.

China Daily, which was accessed in Chinese, was shown to have a much greater level of propaganda usage. The notable difference between the two publications was that all of the articles containing propaganda in *China Daily* were analysed from one day, while the results of *People's Daily* were derived from multiple days.

The overall scores of propaganda were as follows: China in first place with a propaganda score of 202, the United States in second place with 149 (accounting the visibility of the right wing) and 146 (accounting the visibility of the left wing), Russia with 140 and France with 135 (right wing) and 136 (left wing).

Attributional framing

This score differed in the two news outlets of Russia, with *RBK* publishing three articles (16.7%) with notions of attributional framing in them, while *RG* published eight (44.4%). The authoritarian leader, in this case, the president of the Russian Federation, Vladimir Putin, appeared in a positive light in multiple articles in *RBK*, while the articles about opposing presidential candidates were all negative. From *RG*, I was not able to identify negative articles about opposition.

In this case Russia did not resemble the U.S. or France in framing the opposition; the attributional framing in this case was used against the West, resembling China.

Cases of Attributional Framing

FIGURE 1: PIE CHART COMPARING THE OVERALL SCORE OF MENTIONS OF THE NOTION OF US V THEM

The descriptive methods of the articles differed as well, with France's *Le Monde* going to extreme lengths against the far-right, and *Le Figaro* publishing negative articles and passive

aggressive notions about the Left, such as “Its objective is to destroy order. His delusional program would lead to destabilising our security forces, the most absurd measure being the elimination of anti-crime brigades which are often the last ramparts against violence in certain neighbourhoods.” (*Le Figaro* 2017)

The category of description was applied to the supporting propaganda criteria as well - this was one of the many ways the characteristics tended to overlap.

This article was an opinion piece article and in a Polarised Pluralist media setting, this sort of polarisation is expected.

The two French news outlets also differed in results and in the way they utilised attributional framing. *Le Monde* appealed to the public with the actuality of the far-right problems and voting for it, with the seven articles in which they mentioned them, while *Le Figaro* attacked the Left directly with highly critical articles.

China’s descriptive writing is similar to France’s, China’s opposition, however, is the Western world, namely the United States. This was the only category where the propaganda level of the two Chinese news outlets coincided with 61,1% of each having attributional framing in their articles. Quotes framing the west such as: “The plan is considered by many experts as an attempt to counter China’s spreading influence, as well as another example of Australia’s hostile gesture towards China,” (*People's Daily* 2018). These sort of statements could also be categorised as frame resonance to distract as well. In this context, Australia’s prime minister was taking a trip to the United States and this is a follow up to a political scandal, in which a Chinese company with ties to the government had paid off an Australian government official.

China has become more aggressive in their foreign policy after Xi Jinping assumed office. (Zhang & Boukes 2019) This could also be due to American representation of China that has been aggressive throughout the years due to politically conflicting ideologies. (Carpenter 2020)

Of the U.S. news outlets *NYT* was more aggressive in their stance against the Republicans than *WSJ*.

One of the surprising results was *WSJ* publishing two articles that vilified China. One of the statements in an article of the United States about China was “the ‘core’ designation comes with fangs,” (*WSJ* 2016). In accordance with the Social Responsibility Theory, America tries to spread its values of democracy, however, the U.S. and China have been in an information war, perhaps it is time to rethink this? (Friedman 2023)

Another notable attributional framing method from the U.S. articles analysed, was the difference of reporting the political stance of the director of FBI, James Comey, who released Hillary Clinton’s top aide’s ex husband’s sexting evidence just days before the election. *WSJ* reported that James Comey was politically neutral and *NYT* reported Comey to be Republican, continuing

with pugnacious allegations of the Republican party and their ‘plan to overthrow Hillary’ as stated “virtually ensuring that it would be quickly publicized by eager Republicans.” (NYT 2016)

In this case France resembled the United States, with differing statements of the current government spending.

The United States framing China proves that Herman and Chomsky’s (1988) ethos against communism and flak against transgressors is being upheld. Followers of the Social Responsibility Theory, will argue that the state is upholding its own values of democracy and capitalism while followers of the Authoritarian Theory, and most likely China, will argue that this is a way for the state to reach its objectives, which is world domination. Whether it be one or the other; the social responsibility aspect is directly undermined with the dissemination of misinformation between the two news outlets of the United States and France.

Signalling

The attributional framing methods most of the time fell under the signalling category as well since the signalling method followed a pattern of ‘this political power is optimal because the opposition is problematic.’

Cases of signalling and attributional framing

APPENDIX 2: LINE GRAPH HIGHLIGHTING THE COINCIDING OF CASES OF ATTRIBUTIONAL FRAMING AND SIGNALLING

The most notable difference in these results is the United States, that often took the approach of attacking the opposing political party of the one supported by the newspaper, instead of actually signalling the optimality of the party supported, with 13 cases of signalling (36.1%) and 20 cases of attributional framing (55.6%) between the two newspapers. The results also differed between the two, with two cases (11.1%) for *WSJ* and 11 cases (61.1%) for *NYT*, the latter following the outline of signalling of ‘democrats are the optimal choice, because the republicans are inferior’, playing the two criteria together.

“Some states have sought to compensate for sluggish sales tax growth with proposals to more widely apply it. The rise of Republican-led statehouses since 2010 has also yielded proposals to cut income taxes...” (*NYT* 2016)

Like attributional framing, the characteristic of signalling was taken from a paper analysing what the press presents in a totalitarian country in a moment of fragility of the central power such as the exchange of power.

For Russia and China, as authoritarian countries experiencing a slight tip of power, some form of signalling is expected (Boussalis, et al. 2023). The notable results of these, however, are those of the democracies and the differences of their publications.

While *Le Monde* did not signal the overwhelming power of the left, seven of their articles (39%) were informative of the dangers and the countries’ history with the far-right, contrasting *Le Figaro*.

WSJ contrasted *NYT* to extremities. 61% of the articles of *NYT* had notions of signalling while *WSJ* had 11%. Puglisi (2006) has found that *NYT* has historically been showing partisanship to the Democrats before the elections. Could the preference of the political party be the attribute of ownership or could it be due to market demand? Whatever it is, it does not adhere to the ideals of the Social Responsibility Theory. It also raises the question whether left-leaning or right-leaning newspapers can ever be the true constituents of the Theory.

Cases of signalling

APPENDIX 3: DIFFERENCES BETWEEN PUBLICATIONS AND NOTIONS OF SIGNALLING

Another notable difference of publications were the Russian news outlets, *RBK* having two cases (11.1%) of signalling in their publication and *RG* having 10 (55.6%), the latter being the more professional and objective of the two. This may be due to *RBK*'s historical watchdog position, signalling journalistic professionalism, as compared to *RG*.

The pattern of *China Daily*, the website accessed in Chinese, having more notions of propaganda than the website of *People's Daily* that was accessed in English, is a norm for all the other categories except for the previously mentioned attributional framing. It can only be speculated, why this is the case – could it be due to the semantics of Chinese, given that the language is full of interpretive phrases, such as the word for America, "Měiguó", or literally "the beautiful country"? Could it be that China is trying to hide their use of propaganda on their people from the West? The results of the articles differed on the English version of *China Daily* as well, it can only be speculated why.

While the Chinese news outlets were portraying aspects of valency, the main way that Russia was characterised with the signalling criteria was Putin appearing in a movie called *World Order 2018*, where he preached Russia's greatness while framing the United States as the enemy.

Visibility

Visibility of a political party or a leader has been the subject of research ever since the 2016 U.S. presidential elections due to the immoderate scale of coverage of Donald Trump. (Scacco and Coe 2021; Patterson 2016; Reuning and Dietrich 2018). By February of 2016 he had already received \$2 billion dollars in free media, double than any other candidate. Reuning and Dietrich found that this coverage of Trump had a direct impact on polls and is proof of how news channels decide what is newsworthy. While it could be argued that media has the same effect for authoritarian countries which in this case, mainly frame the West, this research entails the citizen government relationship and the visibility of opposing countries was not calculated.

From this research these results were not apparent, given that in the timeframe I picked for my research, evidence of sexting of a congressman close to Hillary Clinton, was released by the FBI and all of the attention was on her, with 13 of the articles (36.1%) mentioning or being about Clinton and eight being about Trump (22.2%) altogether, between the two news outlets.

While there was more coverage on Clinton, overall the visibility score of the Republicans was higher between the two newspapers, with 28 of the 36 articles (77.7%), being about Donald Trump or the Republicans and 25 of the 36 articles (69.4%), being about Clinton or the Democrats.

Visibility of candidates in the four liberally democratic publications

APPENDIX 4: VISIBILITY OF CANDIDATES IN PUBLICATIONS OF LIBERAL DEMOCRACIES

The democracies, in this case, resembled each other, with both of the publications publishing about the same amount of articles of the newspapers readers' popular vote, even though this may

have only been the case due to the Clinton scandal, as suggested by previous research. (Reuning and Dietrich 2018)

There did seem to be a pattern between the two news publications of publishing more articles about the presidential candidate rooted against, with the two right leaning publications publishing more articles attacking the opposition.

Visibility, as found from this research, has been proven to be a characteristic of demagoguery. Two weeks before the elections of Russia, as stated above, Vladimir Putin had appeared in a film called *World Order 2018*, a movie from which quotes from him were published in all Russian news sites including *RBK* and *RG*. The volume of the publication of the quotes tended to differ between the two sites. The visibility score ended up being higher on *RBK* due to Putin appealing to the public through supporting propaganda in articles, which were not published on *RG*, the government's official newsletter. The following was written in an article on the *RBK* news website: "In February, during an awards ceremony, President Vladimir Putin asked Sorokin how long he had been working. Having learned that it was 2.5 years, he said: "It's time to promote you." (*RBK* 2018)

Visibility

APPENDIX 5: VISIBILITY TABLE (POPULAR VOTE OF THE READERS OF THE NEWS OUTLET FOR THE LIBERAL DEMOCRACIES)

China, again, differed in the time frame that all of the results were analysed as well as the results themselves. In *China Daily* 13 out of the 18 articles (72.2%) mentioned Xi Jinping (current president of China; president elected in 2018), with a surprising result of only 5 articles (27.8%) in *People's Daily* mentioning Xi Jinping. These results may be different from the previous leaders, as Jaros and Pan (2018) have concluded that Xi Jinping's media publicity is significantly higher than the previous leaders' emphasising his top-down control.

Executive tone

The executive tone results were applied to the description of the supported power and a clear pattern emerged between the different news outlets and tones of articles about a favoured electorate.

Executive tone used

APPENDIX 6: EXECUTIVE TONE USED FOR A FAVOURED ELECTORATE

I calculated the executive tone used in the American and French news outlets by comparing the language that was used for the favoured electorate, in contrast to the opposed; inspired by Carter and Carter's (2018) methodology, in which they assess this same characteristic of propaganda by comparing the descriptive tone that is used for culture or sports and to what is used for politics. While the two French news outlets used the same amount of executive tone, *NYT* tended to use more favourable language for Clinton in contrast to the critical tone used for Trump than *WSJ* with 33.3% of the articles. These were phrases such as: "Whatever shortcomings Mrs. Clinton

may have as a candidate, Saturday's coordinated effort" in contrast to "Mr. Trump has spent his (candidacy) enriching himself and is unfit to be president". (*NYT* 2016)

The usage of executive tone was also how *People's Daily* and *China Daily* differed from each other in visibility - in this case, also taking into account the article valency difference of the two newspapers; 38.9% for *People's Daily* and 72.2% for *China Daily*.

While *People's Daily* had notions in their articles such as "his speech garnered huge appreciation," (*People's Daily* 2018), then *China Daily* was more extreme of the two in the valency aspect: "The Party Central Committee with Comrade Xi Jinping at its core has set the direction and made plans, united and led the whole Party and the people of all ethnic groups in the country to overcome difficulties and forge ahead, and promoted the cause of the Party and the country to achieve all-round groundbreaking historic achievements and profound changes. fundamental historical changes." (*China Daily* 2018)

RBK was the one of the two Russian outlets that appeared to be using a subservient tone, when describing Putin. Just like with the previous criteria, *RG* differed from *RBK*. These findings go to show the complicated workings of media in a long-time competitive democracy that lacks transparency completely.

Supporting propaganda

While the usage of supporting propaganda was highlighted in China with 63.9% of the articles analysed containing supporting propaganda, with, again, a difference between the publications. America was not far off with 58.3% of all their articles containing supporting propaganda, this time the results of the two publications looked the same.

The U.S. used tactics like publishing an article of a Donald Trump supporter, who happened to be the father of an aid who was killed by the Islamic State, (*WSJ* 2016) .

China appeared again with a strong valency aspect as well, ensuring that the current government and Xi Jinping care for the 'rejuvenation of China and the livelihood of people': "We must persist in treating the people's small things as our own big things, start with things that the people care about, start with things that satisfy the people, and lead the people to continuously create a better life!" At the 19th National Congress of the Communist Party of China, Xi Jinping's deep and rich voice not only echoes in the ears of the representatives of the 19th National Congress, but also resonates in the hearts of hundreds of millions of Chinese people." (*China Daily*, 2018)

Supporting propaganda

APPENDIX 7: SUPPORTING PROPAGANDA USAGE BETWEEN THE TWO COUNTRIES

Russia and France did not appeal to the emotions of people as much, however, France's *Le Monde*, in light of the far-right movement, published highly descriptive articles of the dangers of the far-right. One example of this is an article titled "In these troubled times ..." (*Le Monde* 2017), that recalls Europe's history with the far-right. *Le Figaro* stayed reporting about the Left.

Le Monde is an example of how journalism is fulfilling its watchdog role. Even though it has been done through appealing to the readers' emotions, it is clearly outlining the values of the society and fulfils the journalistic role as the watchdog of a democracy while the U.S. is mainly appealing to the voters. It could be argued that *Le Monde* does appeal to the Social Responsibility Theory here.

Conclusion

In true communist fashion, the Chinese media can be described by Lenin as a, "collective propagandist, collective agitator...collective organizer" (Lenin 1927: 114), with news being full of valency, praising words for the party in power and signalling words of China's greatness; Chinese media fulfils the role of being a collective agitator and and organiser. Meanwhile Russia uses a much more clandestine way to disseminate information; be it the differences of the articles published on the two news websites - one of the websites belonging to the government is by default a vehicle of propaganda, the other not so much. This may be due to electoral constraints that the Russian leader experiences. (Carter and Carter 2018)

While their model of information dissemination undoubtedly creates an echo chamber of the whole country, the liberally democratic countries are experiencing echo chambers, as well, from political polarisation. (Newman and Fletcher 2017)

The press in the two liberal countries analysed in this research, are knowingly advocating their own partisanship, aware that the reader is passive. This can be concluded from the two examples of the countries' news outlets publishing differing information from each other. This leaves the reader with the question of: what do I believe?

In China it is a norm to produce overly saturated pieces about the current government or leader in order to, as the Authoritarian Theory states, progress the state's objectives; America's and France's news outlets in result create political polarisation (Milacic 2021). In Russia and China, it is a norm for its leader to have the hold of visibility in newspapers, knowingly setting the news values and directly having an effect over what the reader will deem important. As of right now, the liberal countries are disregarding the importance of visibility (Mateus 2017) and are appealing to the readers with the extremities of the far right or by displaying a populist leader like Donald Trump, which directly results in them gaining popularity and a platform (Dietrich and Reuning 2018). Maybe it is time to look towards authoritarian countries to advance democracy?

Bernard Cohen (1963) has said that the press may not be telling people what to think, as much as they are telling them what to think about; essentially, the more coverage a topic receives, the more attention it will get from the readers. (Coleman et al. 2009)

It could be stated that the hypodermic needle theory does hold water and is recognised by the liberal news outlets in moments when it is necessary for the news outlet to advocate their partisanship but less, when it does not result in more newspaper sales. It can be argued that this is the reason why Donald Trump is gaining as much attention in the media as he was nine years ago during his initial campaign.

The difference between the United States and France is that the U.S. is not subject to any state intervention. However, this may all change with Donald Trump's pressing promises to end the First Amendment of the United States' constitution, which is the freedom of speech. (CNN 2023; Reporters Without Borders 2023)

Humprecht et al. (2022) have written of the demise of the Liberal archetype, that the United States has been categorised in Hallin's and Mancini's model, and this research proves that. The press in the United States experiences very high levels of political parallelism and weak professionalism. It plays into the spin and agenda setting, and, as stated by Newman and Fletcher, creates distrust in media from the public. (2017)

France and the U.S. do not ideally adhere to the Social Responsibility Theory. If some of the other countries in the world which do have a public service broadcasting platform were to be analysed, could it be concluded that they adhere to the Social Responsibility Theory? Even as the ideal protectors of democracy (Siebert et al. 1963), Trump has become a worldwide phenomenon, and it could be speculated that even the public service broadcasting platforms are

giving him a platform due to their constitutional role as protectors of freedom of speech, meaning that there will always be innate bias.

Siebert et al. have stated in their Libertarian Theory of Journalism that journalism was to be an extralegal check on the government. (1963)

The examples here, however, resemble their description of the Authoritarian Theory, being that the units of communication support and advance the policies of the government in power in order for it to achieve its objectives. The supported unit is not a government in power in the democracies case, it is instead the political party and political elite that the newspaper represents for sales. (Akhvan-Majid 1991)

In accordance with the Libertarian Theory news outlets are, as well as disseminating information, trying to entertain and gain sales, however, when does appealing to the reader get in the way of trustworthy news?

Journalism has been a direct link of the public sphere and government in liberal democracies.

Even though more and more people are getting their information from sources other than news outlets, looking at China and Russia, it can be concluded that our news outlets are still a vital part of the information dissemination process and should not be disregarded. (Zoniga and Goyanes 2021)

Following the example of the European Union passing the Media Freedom Act in March of 2024 to protect journalists from political interference, perhaps right now is the moment when all functioning democracies rethink the Libertarian Theory, and start adhering to the Social Responsibility Theory.

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APPENDICES

APPENDIX 1: CODING MANUAL

Characteristic of propaganda	Description	Characteristics
Attributional framing	Us v them	<p>Represented power is ultimate because x and y</p> <p>Negative articles about opposition</p> <p>Negative connotations</p>
Frame resonance to distract	Distract the readers from the political party or government with the framing of news and events	<p>Sporadic positive article of supported power</p> <p>Negative connotation of opposition for own failures</p> <p>Distractive methods</p>
Frame resonance to attract	Attention to the political party or government and cause with the framing of news and events	<p>Articles released praising the party represented in light of an event</p> <p>Appealing to readers emotions with history</p>
Signalling	Signalling the overwhelming power of represented power	Articles released highlighting the strengths of said power

		Highlighting the failures of opposition in order to highlight supported power
Legitimation approach	Legitimising represented power	Comparison to opposition Why represented power is ultimate
Supporting propaganda	Increasing realisation of ideals by highly emotional or non-rational way	Overtly appealing to the readers emotions about opposition Overtly appealing to the readers emotions about represented power Using manipulation tactics and adjectives such as kids.
Valency	Overwhelming descriptive words	Excessive use of adjectives
Executive tone	Differing tone used for represented power	Comparison of tone of articles of opposition v represented power Executive tone used for authoritarian leader
Visibility index	Number of times of appearance, having an article centred around a power	Article mentions Articles centred around supported power or opposite power

APPENDIX 2: CODING SCHEDULE

Propaganda Characteristic	Article mention	Le Figaro	Le Monde	The New York Times	The Wall Street Journal	RBK	Rossiyaska ya Gazeta	People's Daily	China Daily
Attributional framing:	'Represented unit is ultimate because opposition is not'	4	4	10	2	1	5	10	9
	Negative articles about opposition	4	5	3	6	-	6	7	9
	Negative connotations	7	4	5	-	2	7	4	8
	Mentions in articles highlighting the weaknesses of opposition	7	4	8	6	-	5	9	7
Frame resonance to distract:	Sporadic positive article about supported unit in the case of a tip in power of supported unit by framing news and events	3	2	3	5	7	7	-	9
	Negative connotations about opposition for own mishap by framing news and events	3	5	10	-	-	6	6	7
	Aim to distract attention away from any weaknesses of supported power	3	6	6	4	7	7	8	9
Frame resonance to attract:	Articles appealing to the reader by framing events and news, highlighting supported power	7	4	6	6	5	7	6	9

	Attracting the reader to the supported power through appealing with causes important to them	4	6	6	7	9	6	7	9
Signalling:	Articles released highlighting the strengths of supported power - why it is the ultimate choice	4	2	9	-	-	9	5	9
	Highlighting the failures of opposition in comparison to the superiority of power supported	8	7	10	2	2	3	8	8
Legitimation approach:	Highlighting supported power's strengths and legitimacy of opposing the opposition	2	1	7	4	7	9	6	7
	Comparison to opposition; why the supported power is superior	3	4	7	7	7	4	8	6
	Legitimising the cause of the power supported	3	5	4	6	8	8	8	9
Supporting propaganda :	Displaying emotionality	2	5	4	4	-	5	7	12
	Mentioning of matters of value such as family, overall utopian welfare in order to advance supported power	2	-	6	5	-	5	7	9
	Highlighting the sympathy of supported power	2	5	8	6	5	7	6	9
Valency:	Excessive use of adjectives	6	8	7	6	1	5	7	13

Executive tone:	Positive tone used for the supported power in contrast to the negative one used for opposition	6	6	6	3	-	-	-	-
	Executive tone used for an authoritarian leader as compared to other articles	-	-	-	-	13	2	5	16
Visibility index:	Articles about opposed power	11	9	11	6	-	-	-	-
	Articles of supported power	6	5	11	9	14	6	5	13

FINDINGS**FRANCE**

PROPAGANDA CHARACTERISTIC	LE MONDE (LEFT LEANING)	LE FIGARO (RIGHT LEANING)	OVERALL SCORE
Signalling	7	12	19
Us v them / attributional framing	7	10	17
Visibility*	5	6	11
Legitimation approach	5	6	11
Frame resonance to attract	9	11	20
Frame resonance to distract	8	7	15
Supporting propaganda	6	6	12
Executive tone	6	6	12
Article valence	8	6	14

*- visibility of party supported by newspaper

VISIBILITY TABLES

R - right L - left FR - far right FL - far left

PRESIDENTIAL CANDIDATE	ARTICLES IN LE FIGARO	IN LE MONDE
------------------------	-----------------------	-------------

MARINE LE PEN (FR)	2	6
JEAN LUC MENCHON (FL)	5	2
EMMANUEL MACRON (L)	7	3
FRANCOIS FILLON (R)	3	2
BENOIT HAMON (L)	2	1

POLITICAL PARTY SUPPORTED	LE MONDE	LE FIGARO
LEFT	5 (centre left)	11
RIGHT	9	6

PROPAGANDA SCORE W/O VISIBILITY = 120

PROPAGANDA SCORE OF VISIBILITY OF THE LEFT = 136

OF THE RIGHT = 135

AMERICA

PROPAGANDA CHARACTERISTIC	NEW YORK TIMES (LEFT LEANING)	WALL STREET JOURNAL (RIGHT LEANING)	OVERALL SCORE
Signalling	11	2	13
Us v them / attributional framing	11	2 // 7**	20
Visibility*	11	9	20
Legitimation approach	10	10	20
Frame resonance to attract	8	8	16
Frame resonance to distract	11	6	17
Supporting propaganda	10	11	21
Executive tone	6	3	9
Article valence	7	6	13

*- visibility of party supported by newspaper

** // signifying that two articles were framing other countries and the latter was framing the other party

VISIBILITY TABLE

SUBJECTS ACCOUNTED FOR VISIBILITY	THE NEW YORK TIMES	THE WALL STREET JOURNAL
DONALD TRUMP	3	5
HILLARY CLINTON	7	6
RIGHT WING PARTY	11	9
LEFT WING PARTY	11	6

PROPAGANDA SCORE W/O VISIBILITY = 129

PROPAGANDA SCORE OF VISIBILITY OF THE LEFT = 146

OF THE RIGHT = 149

RUSSIA

PROPAGANDA CHARACTERISTIC	RBK (ECONOMIC LIBERALISM; RIGHT WING POPULISM)	ROSSIYSKAYA GAZETA (BIG- TENT; PRO- PUTIN)	OVERALL SCORE
Signalling	2	10	12
Us v them / attributional framing	3	8	11
Visibility*	14	6	20
Legitimation approach	12	11	23
Frame resonance to attract	11	10	21
Frame resonance to distract	10	10	20
Supporting propaganda	5	7	12
Executive tone	13	2	15
Article valence	1	5	6

PROPAGANDA SCORE = 140

CHINA

PROPAGANDA CHARACTERISTIC	PEOPLE'S DAILY (ENGLISH WEBSITE ACCESS)	CHINA DAILY (WEBSITE ACCESSED IN CHINESE)	OVERALL SCORE
Signalling	8	11	19
Us v them / attributional framing	11	11	22
Visibility*	5	13	18
Legitimation approach	14	15	29
Frame resonance to attract	8	13	21
Frame resonance to distract	9	14	23
Supporting propaganda	9	14	23
Executive tone	5	16	21
Article valence	7	13	20

PROPAGANDA SCORE = 202

ARTICLES READ FOR RESEARCH

AMERICA

THE NEW YORK TIMES

Apuzzo, M., Goldman, A., Schmidt, M. S., Rashbaum, W.K., (2016) Justice Dept. Strongly Discouraged Comey on Move in Clinton Email Case. *The New York Times*. 29.10. Available at: <https://www.nytimes.com/2016/10/30/us/politics/comey-clinton-email-justice.html?searchResultPosition=38> Accessed at: 01.05.2024

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